

On Models, Prediction, and Scientific Roles Thereof: Commentary on Sanbonmatsu et al. (2025)

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We commend Sanbonmatsu et al. (2025) for centring metatheory and metamodel as remedies to “difficult research problems”. However, we wish to depart from their conceptualisation of what models are and what role they play in psychological theorising. Under computationalism, models are not a container for observations through being fit to neurobehavioural data and should not be held to the standard of providing us with numerical predictions. Computational cognitive models can only play their role of mediating from theory to data and back, if and only if we buttress their special status against confusions with other model types, such as with inferential statistical models of the data. This is a realistic goal for our fields. Ultimately, theory crisis or no, blurring the boundary between model, theory, and data in our metatheoretical calculus, results in many of the problems all authors have pointed out.

Keywords: metatheory, formal model, computationalism, cognitive science, prediction, theory crisis

Sanbonmatsu et al. (2025) claim that there is no theory crisis; that theories in psychological science cannot live up to standards proposed by various other authors by definition, and so ideas for improving theorising are problematic because they are unrealistic. At the same time — demonstrating themselves how standards in psychological science could be improved — they take pains to elaborate on why and how they think models are not theories; and instead they foreground the role of prediction, which we have argued will not improve theory-building and evaluation. Herein, we examine their conclusion that we and others have set impossible standards for theories.

We emphatically agree that models are not theories, but must explain that other confusions about the nature of models are just as important to avoid in our metatheoretical calculus (Guest, 2024; Guest & Martin, 2023). For instance, when the authors state “psychology should turn more to formal modelling to increase rigor and improve understanding and prediction” (Sanbonmatsu et al., 2025, p. 2), we cannot but raise an eyebrow or two. We believe this is *quod erat demonstrandum*: formal modelling and “improvements [to] under-

standing” come about through theorizing. To wit, “a lack of metatheoretical understanding” (p. 14) is indeed a core driver of what is often framed as a crisis in theory, *pace* quibbles on the label or actuality of such a crisis.

Furthermore, it appears we diverge on a key concept: *what a model is* — what the role of models within computationalism is and why we should care about them. We will address these fundamental differences between our views below. On the one hand, we of course support the general suggestion that “metatheoretical understanding [is] essential for addressing many scientific problems” (Sanbonmatsu et al., 2025, p. 14). On the other, we reject the notion that prediction relates straightforwardly to what we seek. It instead causes metatheoretical and metamethodological problems — namely confusion between what constitutes a theory obtaining versus what is circumstantial or correlational. And such, we suggest that it is the scramble for so-called prediction that causes “theories in psychological science [to] be vague, weak, and lacking in parsimony, falsifiability, and predictiveness” (p. 14). Therefore, our goals below are twofold:

- a) to clarify what *our* approach to theory and models is and proposes, especially for junior scholars entering the field, and with respect to what role prediction plays in our modelling; and
- b) to further the scholarly exchange of ideas on contemporary theorising, formal and otherwise, which is under attack in the context of artificial intelligence (AI) and

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promote discussion of related ontological issues on what models are for (e.g. Guest & Martin, 2023, 2025; Guest & van Rooij, 2025; van Rooij & Guest, 2026).

To preface the below, it is likely that the authors agree with us that confusions or mergers between models, data, and theories are detrimental, i.e., they say “models are not theories.” (Sanbonmatsu et al., 2025, p. 12) Indubitably, models are not theories. They are, as we shall explain below, cognitive instruments that can serve different theoretical and metatheoretical roles. For instance, models can be mediators between theory and data (Guest & Martin, 2021), computational specifications (Blokpoel & Guest, 2026; Cooper & Guest, 2014), or tools for thinking (Blokpoel & van Rooij, 2021–2025; van Rooij, 2022). This is called the pragmatic view (Winther, 2025): “models are partially independent of both theories and the world [...] and so can be used as instruments of exploration in both domains” (Morrison & Morgan, 1999, p. 10). Presaging our points, we wish to warn the authors and others of the confusion happening on the other end: thinking models and data are inexorably intertwined. The type of models we are interested in are *neither* theories *nor* of the data. When models become enmeshed with the data they cannot perform their mediatory role.

The Role of Models in Computational Cognitive Science

First, **models are not of a single type**. On the one hand, and for the purposes of clarity and conciseness, we will sideline models created in aid of inferential statistics, e.g. frequentist or Bayesian models that directly represent the data, as opposed to model some aspect of a mechanistic or functional psychological theory. These models are indeed fully of the data. On the other hand, we will focus only on theories and their models under computationalism, and even more specifically ones that aid in explaining (e.g. Woody, 2015). As Morrison and Morgan (1999) say:

models function as a separate tool amongst the arsenal of available scientific methods. [...] Models join with measuring instruments, experiments, theories and data as one of the essential ingredients in the practice of science. (p. 36)

To understand the models we are interested in, we must first slightly zoom out. *Computationalism* is the idea that cognition can be understood as a form of computation. That is to say that computational formalisms (found in formal theories and their subsumed models) are appropriate descriptions for describing and understanding cognition. The promise of computationalism is not — and never has been — as quoted above to “improve prediction”. In fact prediction of the type implied by such statements is not only irrelevant, but a red herring and therefore at odds with cognitive modelling (e.g., Guest et al., 2025). Whence the raised eyebrows.

Second, **numerical point prediction is not something we can nor should expect**. Sanbonmatsu et al. (2025), by involving prediction without any caveats, constate that they see models as fit-to-data models and not as cognitive models; they have slipped into assuming that both are of the same type. We can instead consider other forms of prediction — often not labelled as such in a formal setting — as desiderata. Numerical prediction is flimsy, theoretically inert, and often contra building the very scientific understanding we wish to nurture and support.

Qualitative prediction is a different beast altogether. An informative example from the history of science is that the tides were numerically predicted for centuries before we collectively decided on a scientific explanation (Deacon, 2018; Hughes, 2006). Namely that the Sun’s and Moon’s gravities cause tides. This latter understanding, as opposed to the precision-based numerical one that only helped us decide when the tides came in and out and by how much, is what scientific understanding is about. Gravity causing tides is a scientific explanation of the phenomenon, and it references no numerical values (Cartwright, 1983).

This bears repeating. Bede in 725 C.E. *quantitatively* described that “[t]he sea reflects the course of the Moon” (translated by Wallis, 1999, p. 84) and more than a millenium later Lord Kelvin and others built analogue computers called tide-predicting machines (Thomson, 1881). None of these — while amazing feats of mathematics, observation, and engineering — bring about the knowledge of gravity needed for the canonical modern scientific explanation. No amount of numerical predictions, statistical correlations of models to data, give us theory. No amount of putting the data into a model gives us a scientific explanation. As Catherine Z. Elgin (2017) underlines:

Newton’s law of gravity enables us to recognize that the moon’s staying in orbit, the ebb and flow of the tides, and the apple’s falling from the tree are fundamentally the same sort of thing. (p. 264)

None of these realisations are substantively numerical.

Relatedly, informative examples exist of how our cognition — of which science is an instance (Hesse, 1954; Nersessian, 2008; Rich et al., 2021) — can accurately quantitatively predict what happens when we drop a drinking glass. Even if the glass bounces or otherwise does not break (perhaps the floor was carpeted or it fell a very short distance), our ability to qualitatively predict what happens when glass is dropped remains unchanged. Parallels to cognition are theoretically productive because these dispositional properties (e.g., glass is breakable, sugar is soluble; Ryle, 1949) are conceptually related to cognitive capacities (see below). For instance, it is noteworthy that either way, whether the glass shatters, the robustness of the prediction remains, contains no numerical values, and is useful. Besides, the glass shards, their shapes

and locations, are chaotic and thus, unpredictable as we know from basic physics (Guest, Nuñez Hernández & Blokpoel, 2026). All we *can* know is what we do know: glass when dropped breaks. The rest is intractable or uncomputable. A mistake on predicting what will happen to the dropped glass in a deep way, e.g., if it floats upwards, *will* cause severe updates: perhaps we are dreaming, have launched into space, or are experiencing parabolic aircraft flight.

All this is to say that quantitative predictive power is not an important feature of formal theorising — not part of scientific understanding nor a signifier of a good model. Computational cognitive science is not about numerical point prediction. As a subset of the authors explain:

Just because a model correlates with neural and behavioral data, it is not sufficient for us to infer that the model is performing cognition: correlation does not imply cognition. (Guest & Martin, 2023, p. 224)

And related to that, correlations are also not sufficient to infer the model captures our intuitions or verbal theories well. Putting data points directly into models through fitting them to the data makes them models of the data; not what our type of modelling is about. This is not a metatheoretical virtue we seek and not part of our metamethodology (Blokpoel & Guest, 2026; Guest, 2024; Guest et al., 2025). And in fact such types of models when used uncritically can cause deep issues with our own understanding of what understanding is (Chirimuuta, 2021; Guest, Nuñez Hernández & Blokpoel, 2026; Sullivan, 2022).

Third, **cognitive capacities are the main target of theorising** — so another phrasing we wish to somewhat push back on is: “By articulating the processes that may lead to a phenomenon, [...] models connect theories to the real world in a testable way” (Sanbonmatsu et al., 2025, pp. 11–12). While of course models are *of* phenomena, we wish to model, and generally understand and describe, cognitive capacities. *Cognitive capacities*, such as vision, categorisation, navigation, and so on, are not phenomena in a straightforward way. Capacities can be meaningfully detached from individual phenomena, if by phenomenon we mean observations, datasets, or psychological effects. This point bears highlighting because the authors make no mention of cognitive capacities, which are the core explanandum, what is to-be-explained, of neurocognitive and psychological theorising (Egan, 2017; Ryle, 1949; Schellenberg, 2018; van Rooij & Baggio, 2021). And they are not alone — many neglect to centre capacities, but this is something easy to change if we remember to foreground what our fields actively seek.

Fourth, **metatheoretical calculi in practice are messy**. Sanbonmatsu et al. (2025) describe how they see the process of formal modelling, which we agree is an iterative loop guided by the theoretician (Guest & Martin, 2021; van Rooij & Baggio, 2021). On evaluation of models they remark that:

Mismatches between the modeled behavior and observed behavior generally lead to the rejection of a model. Models are subsequently modified and refined to map reality more closely and provide a better understanding of the study phenomena. (p. 12)

Rejecting theories or models is a tricky process. There are ample cases where models which diverge from human neurobehavioural data are rationalised in other ways (e.g., by claiming humans indeed behave that way; see section: *Inference Rules in (Mis)use*, Guest & Martin, 2023) as well as cases where explanatory, logical, or conceptual inconsistencies are tolerated when model revision would be more appropriate (van Rooij et al., 2012). Under a strict reading, where the authors say “models tend to be falsifiable but not provable” (Sanbonmatsu et al., 2025, p. 13) we cannot but agree. However, the landscape of reasoning over models — and thus, the metatheoretical calculus in use — contains many cases of explaining away the mismatches between empirical data and model output. And indeed such reasoning may result from “flaws in the grounding and construction of theories, and other metatheoretical and metamethod issues” (p. 14).

Fifth, **models are not (of the) data**. The intention to “map reality more closely [to] provide a better understanding” (in the blockquote above) should ring alarm bells for any theoretician (Guest & Martin, 2025). On why making our theories, maps, resemble the territory as closely as possible, perhaps considering the case of the actual map is helpful. Lewis Carroll (1893) has a compelling such example wherein a fictional character proudly proclaims:

“We actually made a map of the country, on the scale of a mile to the mile!” [And when asked if the map has been used, explains:] “It has never been spread out[. T]he farmers objected: they said it would cover the whole country, and shut out the sunlight! So we now use the country itself, as its own map, and I assure you it does nearly as well.” (n.p.)

This confusion, and furthermore merger, between explanandum and explanans, map and territory, theory and observations, are what cause some of the most deleterious and damaging issues in contemporary theorising, especially when under the influence of the technology industry’s logic (Guest & Martin, 2023, 2025; van Rooij et al., 2024). Is this not what constitutes a crisis? The ontological blurring between our formalisms, models, theories, and what we wish to understand, such as capacities, phenomena, data generating processes, means that models cannot play their role as mediators between theory and data (Guest & Martin, 2021; Morrison & Morgan, 1999). Not being clear on what the role of models and the purpose of creating them is, is an emerging status quo that we believe is harmful to theorising.

Do not “shut out the sunlight!”

The crisis consists precisely in the fact that the old is dying and the new cannot be born; in this interregnum a great variety of morbid symptoms appear. (Gramsci, 1930, p. 556)

There is actually a sea change with respect to theory and metatheory in psychology unfolding over the last two decades (Guest & Martin, 2025; van Rooij & Baggio, 2020). Material conditions as well as ideological positions have been shifting. We are witnessing due to AI, which is deeply historically and presently intertwined with psychology, the “severing of society from its previous moorings.” (McQuillan, 2026) Such as the ontological confusion on what a model is, which is turbocharged by claims that AI can replace theory, participants, scientists, educators, and ourselves (Guest, Suarez et al., 2026; Guest & van Rooij, 2025; van Rooij & Guest, 2026).

Sanbonmatsu et al. (2025) state that “there is nothing temporary about the current state of theory in psychology.” (p. 14) On the one hand, theory has always had issues, but these are not in part or whole due to the nature of our phenomena. Pessimistic meta-induction, the underdetermination of theory by data, even multiple realizability or the method of multiple explanations, and more, apply to all science (Guest, Blokpoel & van Rooij, 2026; Tsouna, 2023). On the other hand and as mentioned above, we are living through attacks on our science from both the outside and inside wherein non-theory and non-science produced by industry players is presented as computational modelling of the phenomena and capacities we study, and worse as theories thereof (van Rooij & Guest, 2026; van Rooij et al., 2024). This is what Sanbonmatsu et al. (2025) rightly warn of: the confusion between model and theory. And so we are living through a turn towards both taking computationalism seriously (the “new” in the Gramsci quote) as well as a turn away from acknowledging the ontological distinction between models, theories, and data (the “morbid symptoms”). The former is not compatible with the latter; and the latter is harmful to all science.

In their final remarks, Sanbonmatsu et al. (2025) praise psychology as a science for our collective achievements. We largely agree, and in fact would go further and say a current turn in philosophy is also in part due to *our* psychological and cognitive scientific achievements (viz. Egan, 2017; Elgin, 2017). So much so that philosophers help computational cognitive scientists, like ourselves, buttress our craft against intrusions. As Frances Egan (2025) says: “I suspect, though, that cognitive scientists would be quite surprised to hear that their theorizing requires supplementation by philosophers” (p. 50). But when Sanbonmatsu et al. (2025) end on the following, we worry: “theories guide the development of models that can predict important psychological outcomes” (p. 15). Quite the opposite! Numerical predictions are ironically within the “unrealistic standards that prevail in science” (p. 15) and it is

actively harmful to prize this within theorising. Statistical or numerical models are almost always “largely wasted effort” (Watt, 2026, n.p.) in our context. As we have explained above, prediction in the numerical sense is not what theories can ever give us, nor what we seek as theoreticians. Confusing statistical models and cognitive models directly undermines theory (Guest & Martin, 2021; Guest & van Rooij, 2025; van Rooij & Baggio, 2021; van Rooij & Guest, 2026).

In contrast, realistic and useful bars to meet exist for the theoretician. Iris van Rooij (2008) and Frances Egan (2025) say “tractably specifiable” may be a basic requirement for theory and related models. Tractability has *nothing* to do with the data. And many potential metatheoretical considerations are discussed by Olivia Guest (2024), including avoiding forceful unification or homogenisation.

[W]e must reject the current mainstream view [within modelling]: no amount of high scores on benchmarks, or any other correlatory evidence, can ever pile up high enough to graduate to a causal claim. (Guest, 2026, p. 17)

Ultimately, computational cognitive models are not more useful if fit to the data. If they are useful and obtain, then they may happen to match the data. But not fitting the data does not mean they are not good models. In fact, when we prioritise numerical prediction over explanation, we obfuscate the purpose of cognitive models, and thus hinder theorizing rather than bolstering it. In such cases, models can lose their ability — core to their identity — to mediate between theory and observation, because the more they become statistical models of the data, the less they remain cognitive models, and the less they can explain. Therefore, regardless of whether there is a specific crisis in theory, blurring the meanings of scientific terms like model and data is disruptive. Theoretical and modelling work is possible only when the breadth of the role that models play is recognized, understood, and nurtured.

The neuro-, psychological, and cognitive sciences, and computational communities therein, should not be underestimated. We should not be content with theories and models that prioritize numerical correlation over explanation that blur their metatheoretical ties, and which render our fields closer to pseudoscience. Computational cognitive science in principle can and should do more than merely model data.

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